

Capacity building requirements for Copernicus Inland Waters

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Executive summary

Capacity building is a key element in improving the impact of Copernicus in the inland water domain. In particular, this includes building the capacity of potential and existing users of Copernicus services and products, among the Capacity programme itself, and within the wider system. The report summarises the capacity building recommendations made in the deliverables submitted from Work Packages 1-5, alongside results from an extensive survey from different segments of the water domain, and external sources. The overall strategy for building capacity is summarised in the Figure below; 1) Building capacity among existing and potential users to maximise the uptake of existing products and Services, 2) Ensuring the supply of products and Services is user-driven, determined by the requirements, abilities and resources available to users, and 3) Enhance the policy and funding framework, as well as existing networks, to facilitate the incorporation of EO within the water domain.

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

1.1 Water-ForCE

The Horizon-2020 project Water-ForCE (Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation) will develop a Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services.

The Roadmap will contain:

- Analysis of user communities' landscape
- Analysis on how Copernicus water-related services can support policy development and monitoring of their implementation
- Gap analysis of the Copernicus water-related service portfolio
- Identification of future potential higher-level biogeochemical products
- Technical requirements for future Copernicus sensors to improve the water-related service portfolio
- Proposal for organising in-situ measurement networks to validate Copernicus remote sensing and modelling products and to provide complementary data not collected by remote sensing
- Proposal on how to define relationships between Core Services and Downstream services
- Scenarios of the most optimal delivery of water services to different user communities.

The Water-ForCE project is coordinated by the University of Tartu (Estonia) with 20 participating organisations from all over Europe. It connects experts in water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors.

This report is part of Work Package 6 (WP6) "Roadmap" which brings together the results from WPs 1-5 into a capacity building programme (this deliverable D6.1), research and innovation priorities (D6.2), opportunities for business innovation and services (D6.3) and, ultimately, an actionable roadmap (D6.4).

1.2 Scope of the report

Task 6.1 Co-develop Requirements for Capacity building requirements for Copernicus Inland Waters. Within this task, the needs and recommendations for capacity building from work packages 1-5 have been collated. This capitalises on the stakeholder engagement throughout the projects, including dissemination events, interviews, webinars, workshops and surveys. These outputs were organised to discuss individual, organisational and system level capacity building. Existing relevant programmes and projects for capacity building of Copernicus Inland waters were also reviewed, to determine the degree to which the objectives are being met. Finally, the report closes with a recommendation on how to monitor, evaluate progress towards the Copernicus Inland Waters capacity building objectives.

1.3 Definitions used in the report

Capacity: “the ability of people, organisations and society as a whole to manage their affairs successfully” (OECD, 2006).

Capacity building / development: “the process whereby people, organisations and society as a whole unleash, strengthen, create, adapt and maintain capacity over time” (OECD, 2023). In this report, the term “capacity building” is regarded as interchangeable with the term “capacity development”. In this report, we use the term “Capacity Development”, as the preferred term by the OECD (EPRS, 2007).

2. Sources of information in this report

The data and information presented in this report derives from a number of sources. Firstly, many recommendations have been made within the Water-ForCE deliverables, which have been results from the expert consortium, the advisory board, interaction with working groups and many stakeholder or user engagement events. The full list of Capacity building recommendations are provided in Annex 1. Where recommendations are mentioned they will include the link to the deliverable, where further details are presented. Many of these recommendations are the result of expert review of the Copernicus Services and Products or the result of user engagement, such as workshops and surveys (e.g. **D1.1** includes surveys at stakeholder workshops, **D3.4** presents survey results from water quantity working group, **D5.1** presents survey results from a water quantity and modelling workshop).

Figure 1. Summary of the sources of information presented in this report.

In addition to the deliverables, a very important source of information is the user-based Capacity building survey (hereafter called “Water-ForCE CB survey”) which was completed

by 336 people in multiple languages (English, Mandarin, Spanish, French and Portuguese) from various sectors within the water domain. The [survey in English](#) is still open, and the full results as of April 2023 are presented in the Annex. The survey has covered most segments of the water domain; including various organisational sectors, locations and roles of the individuals (Figure 2.). All of the participants self-identified as participating in the water domain.

Figure 2. Segmentation of the survey responses for the Water-ForCE capacity development survey in terms of 1) the sector in which the organisation is part of, 2) the role of the individual completing the survey, and 3) the location of the organisation (from top to bottom). The percentage value of the 336 respondents is also shown in text and reflected by the size of the box.

Finally, external sources of information were also used from academic journals and reports. In particular, the European Association of Remote Sensing companies (EARSC) survey which is completed by EO companies each year. In this report we used information from the [2020](#), [2021](#) and [2022](#) surveys. Market reports were reviewed from PwC for [2016](#) and [2019](#), as well as the interim report from PwC in [2017](#) and the Copernicus ex-ante benefits assessment in [2017](#). Another external source is EO and GNSS Market Report from EUSPA for [2022](#). Moreover, various academic and white paper documents were used, including the AquaWater survey published in Agnoli et al., [2023](#) and the EO Africa R&D Facility survey [2022](#). Output from GEO AcquaWatch events were also used and can be found [here](#), as well as GEO Capacity Building Strategy (2006), and many other projects (full list is found in Section 6.4).

3. Capacity development within the Copernicus context

Capacity building and capacity development are terms that originate from the mid-20th century and have been devised by the global development community in the 1990s and early 2000 (European Parliament, 2007). According to The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) definition, adopted by the EU and used widely within the literature, capacity building is the process of creating, strengthening, maintaining and adapting the capacity of individuals, organisations and society as a whole over time. This definition identifies capacity building at three levels; individual, organisational and enabling environment or system (Figure 3). The GEO Capacity Building Strategy (2006) offers further specification for the application of Earth observation. These two sources have been used to devise definitions specifically for this report, with examples relevant to the Water-ForCE project (Table 1).

Figure 3. Levels of capacity building (adapted for our purposes from Porzecanski et al, 2022)

Table 1. Capacity building levels specific for Copernicus (adopted from GEO, 2006 and EU, 2017 definitions). Examples in brackets from Water-ForCE project, which has engaged in all levels of capacity building.

Level	Definition	Example methods (modified from list in Porzecanski et al., 2022)
Individual	<i>The education and training of individuals to be aware of, access, use and develop Earth observation data and products.</i>	<i>Conferences, formal education, information education, mentoring & coaching, needs assessments, peer-to-peer learning, self-directed learning training courses, workshops</i> (e.g., workshops and webinars provided by Water-ForCE)
Organisational	<i>Focused on developing and fostering an environment for the use of Earth observations to enhance decision making. This includes building policies, programs and organisational structures within Copernicus, aimed at enhancing the understanding of the benefits of Earth observation data and products.</i>	<i>Capacity development planning, networks (e.g. peer & professional) human resource management, strategic planning, coordinating co-development, tool kits and practice guides.</i> (e.g., funding coordination projects such as Water-ForCE to assess user capacity building needs)
Enabling environment / System	<i>Coordination of the social system, including upstream, downstream stakeholders, Copernicus providers, global to local users, that sets the overall scope for capacity. Legislative and regulatory frameworks.</i>	<i>Behavioural change interventions (e.g., social marketing campaigns) cross-sectoral planning, institutional analysis, scenario planning.</i> (e.g., Water-ForCE scenario planning)

Capacity building can also be considered in terms of storylines, which define whose capacity is being built and for what purpose. For the Copernicus programme, there are various storylines (Table 2). For example, Copernicus can provide support or resources to current or potential users to develop capacity in the exploitation of Copernicus Services, or simply to increase awareness of EO capabilities. This capacity building might take the form

of educational resources, training and workshops, improvement of the accessibility of Copernicus products or protocols for educating users, but also the creation of new funds or project calls. Within the Copernicus Program as an organisation, there may also be the need to build capacity, for example, by educating and recruiting skilled personnel to allow the Copernicus Program to fulfil its purpose. The Copernicus Program is also concerned with developing capacity to meet evolving technical and sensor requirements, to provide new types of data, or change the way this data is delivered. Data awareness and reaching new end-users may also be considered a capacity building goal, which includes educational aspirations.

Table 2. Storylines for capacity building within the Copernicus Program context.

Action	Subject	Objective		
Enabling, developing or strengthening	potential users	to have understanding of EO satellite capabilities	Individual	
	current users (individual)	to exploit Copernicus products		
	upstream/intermediate users			
	the Copernicus Program		to ensure supply of skilled personnel	Organisational
			to reach more end-users	
			to advance technical abilities and improve data and products	
	Policy / legislation Funding		to enable individuals and organisations to use EO, to advance relevant technologies and remove bottlenecks	Enabling environment / System

The following sections of this report will cover the capacity building requirements for the current and potential users of Copernicus for Water (Section 4); the capacity building requirements of Copernicus to improve the delivery of products and Services (Section 5); and the requirements of an enabling environment to increase the uptake and impact of Earth observation data (Section 6).

4. Individual-level: Building the capacity of potential and existing users for enhanced uptake

Level	Definition	Example
Individual	<i>The education and training of individuals to be aware of, access, use and develop Earth observation data and products.</i>	<i>Conferences, formal education, information education, mentoring & coaching, needs assessments, peer-to-peer learning, self-directed learning training courses, workshops</i> <i>(e.g., workshops and webinars provided by Water-ForCE)</i>

For the impact of the Copernicus Programme to be realised, products and Services need to be taken up by individuals, organisations and enter into workflows that lead to improved decision making. An element of this is ensuring that those who have relevant applications for Copernicus products and Services are aware of the EO data and EO-derived information, that they trust and accept it and that they have the knowledge and skills to utilise it. Capacity building of individuals and organisations to fully utilise existing products and Services is the responsibility of the Copernicus Programme and external organisations, both of which can coordinate, facilitate and directly deliver engagement and training activities that build capacity among individuals. In this section, these activities are discussed. Content is included from WP1-5 (see ANNEX for raw excerpts) and the Water-ForCE CB survey (see Section 2 for survey description and ANNEX for full survey). In short, this section will cover (Figure x);

1. Improving **awareness and attitude** of individuals within the Water domain to Earth observation data, products or information,

2. Providing materials and hosting activities that build **skills and knowledge** that can be used to use EO data and products directly,
3. Tailored capacity building activities for **water agencies** around the world.

Building capacity of current and potential users

Figure 4. Summary of building capacity of current and potential users.

4.1 Awareness and attitude

In the Water-ForCE CB survey “pulse check” section, basic questions were asked to gauge the attitude of the participants to satellite Earth observation data (Figure 5). Overall, there was a common awareness of the potential benefits of EO data, and the vast majority of the respondents thought there would be benefits to themselves or their work. There was a large proportion (39%) that did not know or did not think they had access to EO data at all, which demonstrates an important misconception that needs to be addressed. Additionally, around half of the participants did not feel they had the skills to use EO data. These results suggest that, at least among the group surveyed, there is an overwhelmingly positive attitude towards EO data and the information EO can provide for the water domain. In

contrast, skills and knowledge are a key barrier facing individuals and there is a need to focus on this area.

Results from 336 respondents within the water domain:

Figure 5. Infographic to show the “pulse-check” results from the survey

4.2 Knowledge and Skills

Earth observation data handling and product application has relatively high knowledge and skill requirements, which as shown above (Figure 5) are a barrier to the uptake of potential users. Earth observation applications can require advanced theoretical knowledge and data handling skills. However, providing data in different stages of readiness, tools and platforms can reduce the amount of capacity required to utilise EO-based information. Applications are also highly specific which can make it challenging to provide meaningful tutorials.

In the Water-ForCE CB survey, there was a notable mismatch between the types of training activities delivered and the needs of the respondents. Respondents were asked in which areas their organisation had engaged in capacity building activities, and in which areas further engagement was needed (Figure 6). GIS and Science communications were the only areas where recent capacity building activities scored higher than the need for future engagement. All other areas indicated that not enough capacity building was being done. For some areas, such as *in situ measurements for calibration and validation*, *statistical analysis* and *data visualisation*, a large number of participants reported activities within their organisation to develop capacity, but also identify these areas as needing continued attention in the future. In contrast, various areas presented as having a large mismatch between the amount of activities offered in recent years and the need in the future. These included typically more computational and technical skills including *coupling Earth observation to predictive modelling*, *machine learning AI & deep learning* and *big data analytics*.

COMPARISON BETWEEN RECENT CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES AND THOSE NEEDED

Figure 6. Survey results from 300 respondents within organisations in the water domain showing the difference between capacity building activities held in the last few years and activities which are needed. They are ordered in terms of areas with the greatest difference.

It is also clear that the capacity building needs differ between sectors within the water domain (Figure 7). These differences might be driven by differences in their objectives (e.g., commercial or research), education, resources, organisational structures, and available funding and resources. A few differences are highlighted here, although the number of participants within each group are not well-spread (see Figure 1). None of the participants from the academia sector found a need for improvement in science communications, or theory of remote sensing. Over 40% identified a need for measuring and understanding uncertainty, but there were relatively lower areas for improvement identified relative to private and public sectors. Similarly, none of the participants from the private sector identified a need for improvement within their organisation in terms of the theory of remote sensing. Over 60% identified a need for coupling EO to predictive modelling, and over 50% identified the need for image processing, data visualisation. Over 50% of the participants from the public sector identified a need for image processing and big data analytics. Participants from the NGO sector showed generally no strong needs for capacity building and there were no participants that identified the need for cybersecurity. The participants that selected Other had a very large need for big data analytics (70%) but do not have a unifying sector identity.

A request in multiple deliverables was for tutorials providing an overview of Copernicus, how to choose a parameter depending on your application and basic processing (**D3.1**, **D3.2**, **D5.1**). Further ideas include a DIAS bot to guide new users depending on their needs and expertise (**D5.3**), providing example codes using digital notebooks (e.g., Jupyter) (**D5.3**). This frequently came out of workshops even with experienced users, who reflected on the barriers they faced in first using Copernicus data (**D5.1**, **D3.4**).

AREAS THAT NEED IMPROVEMENT WITHIN ORGANISATION BY SECTOR

Figure 7. Results to the question “areas which need improvement in your organisation” organised as percentages of respondents from each sector which selected the area for improvement.

4.3 Tailored training activities

Developing more tailored training opportunities is vital for the uptake of EO data among specific groups of users or potential users. Such training courses need to demonstrate how EO can be used to meet their specific goals and with knowledge of their current challenges, workflows and capacities. The format for this can differ from the educational facilitators deciding what is important, right down to providing workshops for local users based on exact problems they would like to solve. This type of educational activity may go further to promote the benefits of EO among resistant groups of potential users. This may also be an exchange type activity, where participants can direct the educational programme, or where the facilitator may find out a lot about the user requirements.

Water agencies were frequently singled out within workshop feedback, as a group who can benefit from capacity building, as mentioned in multiple deliverables (**D2.2, D2.3, D5.3, D5.4**). Water agencies within Europe and globally are a group of current/potential users who may need and benefit from greater awareness and knowledge of EO applications. Greater uptake of EO data within water agencies can also support the sustainable development goals (in particular SDG6) (see EO4SDG), or enable member states to meet EU policy reporting regulations. One example of how this can be conducted is through free or subsidised courses such as the Freshwater Quality Monitoring & Assessment course from GEMs/Water, delivered by Cork University, designed for global water managers often receiving international funding (link [here](#)). Another group that is very important is the commercial water industry, which is discussed in detail in D6.3.

4.4 Existing activities

For this section a list was compiled of resources that can be used by individuals or agencies to build individual capacity. Firstly, in grey (Table 4 below) there are a number of resources that are specific to using EO-satellite and remote sensing for inland water quantity and quality (Table 3). The most comprehensive and relevant sources found were the ARSET training documents, recommended in workshops by users (D5.3) and supplied by NASA. Overall, the list of very specific resources for new EO users from the water domain are very few. We did not find any tutorials designed for water managers or for

SDG monitoring (although see platforms in section 5.4; see projects and networks list in section 6.4). Clear challenges exist in producing documentation that can be widely used, given the often specificity of inland water processing. Furthermore, methods are regularly changing within the area of science, for example water quality algorithms are continually developing. Despite this, it is clear that far more resources can and need to be provided for new users, for students and for water agencies to develop technical capacity to monitor water bodies remotely. A secondary list (in green Table 4) shows resources which are also relevant for processing or using EO water data/products, but are not designed for this specific application, for example learning about Earth Observation and remote sensing in general, or necessary coding skills.

Table 3. List of tutorials and educational programmes which are freely available online for using EO-satellite and remote sensing data for inland water quantity and quality.

Description	Access	Link
Global Lakes Sentinel Services	Open	10 - lesson plan
Trevor Platt programme	Application & selection process	'Satellite-based tools for investigating aquatic ecosystems' - Highly relevant, state of the art techniques
ARSET courses (multiple)	Open	recommended course (D3.2 etc). NASA based.
GMES & Africa Learning Platform (one course on water bodies with Sentinel)	Self enrollment needed	Includes one course on water bodies with Sentinel
ICCG Training & Education materials	Open	List of materials include various relevant resources
Water Quality Data Pathfinder - NASA EarthData	Open	Web-browser for finding relevant data and learning about the data provided
EO4GEO training materials	Open	Includes material on specific subjects including flood mapping
Mantel ITN youtube resources	Yes	Lakes, stratification, extreme events on EO
MIT OpenCourseware	Free (no certificate, just courses)	Courses on many things including some relevant physics and coding
DataCamp	Paid	Coding courses
LinkedIn courses	Free Trial	Coding and data processing
MOOC - ESA courses	Open	Includes remote sensing theory, application and data

		processing.
<u>INCC Data Skills Framework</u>	Open	Include framework relevant for understanding skills and steps involved in developing the capacity of EO users.
<u>Planetek Italia</u>	Open	EO practical tutorials available but not water focused.
<u>Planet EO University</u>	Open	EO practical tutorials available but not water focused.

Formalised education (i.e. University degrees), focusing on remote sensing and Earth observation are growing. Undergraduate and Masters degrees can include modules on Earth observation. Some Masters are focused specifically on Earth observation, and a list of 48 courses were found using 'FindaMasters.com' (available [here](#)). In addition, there are various PhD training programmes which focus on Earth observation. This includes [SENSE](#) led by The University of Edinburgh and will train 70 PhD students. Additionally the European Union Agency for Space Programme (EUSPA) has published a Horizon Europe Call in 2022 which may include Innovative Training Networks and has a Earth observation focus (DotSPACE, [2022](#)). The authors of this report are not aware of any specific initiatives to encourage universities to host dedicated EO courses, except Copernicus Academy which recognises this, or any support for universities on how to deliver these course or encourage an audience to existing courses.

5. Organisational-level: Building the capacity of the Copernicus Programme to better meet the needs of the water domain

Level	Definition	Example
Organisational	<i>Focused on developing and fostering an environment for the use of Earth observations to enhance decision making. This includes building policies, programs and organisational structures within Copernicus, aimed at enhancing the understanding of the benefits of Earth observation data and products.</i>	<i>Capacity development planning, networks (e.g. peer & professional) human resource management, strategic planning, coordinating co-development, tool kits and practice guides.</i> <i>(e.g., funding coordination projects such as Water-ForCE to assess user capacity building needs)</i>

The focus of this section is supply-side, ensuring that Copernicus is delivering products that meet the requirements, abilities and the capacity of the users. The necessary format of EO-derived products largely depends on the type of user, and ranges from analysis-ready, information-ready and even decision-ready. Not all of these EO-products need to be delivered by Copernicus, however it is within the scope of the Copernicus Programme for Water to consider who is delivering these products, how far EO derived information is penetrating. Platforms, web browsers and actionable tools can be used to also lower the necessary capacity (e.g., the computational or technological skills) required to access EO-products. Hence, in this section the following aspects will be considered (Figure below);

1. Supply of products that match user requirements,
2. Delivering EO products at different capacity levels
3. Use of platforms and tools to lower capacity needs

Supply-side mechanisms to increase uptake

Figure 8. Summary of supply-side mechanisms to increase uptake of copernicus products and services.

5.1 Supply of products that match user requirements

The supply of products that match the needs and abilities of users is critical to the Copernicus Programme and has been a huge focus of the Water-ForCE project. Product development is largely covered in other deliverables (D6.2, and also D2.5 for water quality products, D3.4 for water quantity products and D3.5 from the lake modelling perspective). In addition to the analysis of other deliverables, the satellite-based information services requirements of the 333 water domain, derived from the CB survey (Figure x). These results demonstrate a predominant interest in flood forecasting information, with a smaller interest in flood monitoring, information on reservoirs and river-flow. Many of the information services listed were not selected by any of the users, which include zz. These results do not reflect the entire water domain or all the relevant end-user sectors. however they do demonstrate the kind of scoping which can be done to ensure that there is a strong customer-base. Another important user requirement was also demonstrated within the CB survey, as a barrier to uptake. This was the lack of in situ validation data, which was the large technical barrier we found. This was similarly noted by Agnoli et al., (2023) as trust in Satellite EO data was closely related to lack of validation data.

Figure 9. Results from CB survey regarding what type of EO-based information users would find most useful.

5.2 Delivering products for different capacity levels

EO products can be delivered in different formats for different users. One way of classifying products in terms of capacity required to use them, is to consider ‘analysis-ready’, ‘information-ready’ and ‘decision-ready’ products. Although definitions vary, the basic idea is explained below. Firstly, analysis-ready products come pre-processed (i.e. with atmospheric correction and cal/val process completed) and are organised in a way for users to start their analysis without investing time in data preparation. Secondly, information-ready products are delivered in units of a given water parameter and therefore can be read intuitively without a strong understanding of remote sensing. Information-ready products have therefore already had the necessary algorithms applied, or modelling, and have been calibrated and validated with in situ data and should come with an uncertainty estimation. Thirdly, decision-ready data is simplified and translated into the language of specific decision-makers, possibly to address a specific question, for example, where is the highest risk of algal bloom, or the greatest flood risk within a region. Such products may no longer be delivered as data, but rather as a single map or a short report. An important note is that as information-ready products place a lot of the control in the providers and the uncertainty becomes less realised by the users.

Table 4. Types of EO products and capacity required to utilise them.

Type of product	Capacity required	Example
Analysis-ready	Understanding of reflectance measurements Understanding of algorithms for water parameters (Big) data handling skills Computational capacity and strong internet Time and effort	Pre-processed reflectance product
Information-ready	Understanding of water parameters Data handling skills Ability to retrieve information from data and	Map of chl-a concentrations

	some understanding of EO data uncertainty	
Decision-ready	Knowledge of risk of given Some understanding of data uncertainty	HAB risk map

5.3 Platforms and tools which reduce capacity

Platforms and tools can also be used to reduce the capacity demanded of users. In particular, web-browsers that allow spatial searches can allow users to investigate data before downloading large amounts of data, they may also allow analysis within the cloud to reduce the need for computational space. Platform-providers are also a key step in the Water Value Chain (see D6.3), necessary for delivering EO-derived information to users in different sectors, but are likely to be delivered downstream rather than by Copernicus Services. Platforms might deliver analysis-, information-, or decision-ready data but possibly just a subset that is relevant to the target audience (e.g., for SDG6 reporting, or for agricultural planning). Platforms are also very important for building capacity as they are a strong educational tool. Some platforms are tailored for particular groups, for example, in Table 5, there are portals listed which could be use by water managers to assess individual water bodies (e.g., The water accounting plus and Blue dot observatory), or complete SDG reporting (e.g., SDG reporting portal and The FreshWater Ecosystems Explorer). Synergy Sentinel Hub in particular has been identified as particularly useful to EO companies in the 2021 EARSC survey. While platforms can enable users with less capacity to process data from scratch (i.e., knowledge, time, effort, data space), they can result in less trust from users who are not involved in the decisions made to process the data.

Table 5. List of additional relevant tutorials and educational programmes which are freely available online.

Other relevant sources	Provider	Notes on the relevance for capacity building
Google Earth Engine	Google	Reduce capacity required to access, download data, can reduce computation capacity etc. Forums also improve sharing of knowledge.

<u>Giovanni NASA</u>	NASA	Similar to Ggoogle Eearth Eengine but even reduces the need for any coding abilities. Does not include Copernicus data.
<u>Synergise Sentinel Hub</u>	Synergise (Copernicus Emergency Service)	Allows access of Copernicus products and is widely used by private industry (EARSC 2021 survey)
Blue Dot Observatory	Synergise	Still in R&D but has the potential to facilitate WFD by providing data at water body level.
Global Water Surface Explorer		developed by DG JRC, UN Environment and Google (See D1.3)
<u>SDG8 Reporting Portal</u>	SDG	Allows automatic SDG using EO data. Limited to few water bodies but demonstrates the type of options available.
<u>The Freshwater Ecosystems Explorer</u> (see D5.4)	SDG	Similarly The FreshWater Ecosystems Explorer has a number of functions which can help with SDG monitoring over time (see D5.4)
<u>The Water Accounting Plus</u> (D3.3)	WFD	(WA+) framework was developed to use open-access remote sensing based data for water accounting at the basin level that can level can be used for WFD. (see D3.3)

6. System level: building an enabling environment

Level	Definition	Example
Enabling environment / System	<i>Coordination of the social system, including upstream, downstream stakeholders, Copernicus providers, global to local users, that sets the overall scope for capacity. Legislative and regulatory frameworks.</i>	<i>Behavioural change interventions (e.g., social marketing campaigns) cross-sectoral planning, institutional analysis, scenario planning. (e.g., Water-ForCE scenario planning)</i>

This section considers the enabling environment can increase the uptake of EO by end-users, or can promote the growth of Copernicus Programme. At the top of this list is policy, and placing EO as a distinct method for reporting on policy and a key part of future policymaking. Second on this list is funding, since lack of financial capital and resources is still a massive barrier to the uptake of EO, even as EO overcomes many of the barriers of traditional methods. Finally, there are networks which are international and intersectoral, enabling the sharing of knowledge, stimulating innovation, and bringing users and providers together at different stages of the value chain. This is summarised below (figure x).

Building an enabling environment

Figure 9. Summary of building an enabling environment for greater uptake of EO Copernicus products and Services.

6.1 Include EO compliance in Policy

Policy is at the forefront of mechanisms which can increase the uptake of EO towards meeting European Water goals (as discussed in more detail in **D6.3**). In summary of D6.3, it is recommended that Earth observation be promoted as a possible option for national completion of the Water Framework Directive or other water related policies within the EU. This means that there should be clear compliance for how to use EO data, dependent on the data available etc. **see Del 5.3** In contrast, Earth observation is being increasingly recognised as a key method in the sustainable development goals. Projects to this cause include EO4SDG etc.

6.2 Funding at different levels

Funding, and the lack of financial capital, is a massive barrier to the uptake of EO, independent of whether there is sufficient knowledge or willingness to use EO. This

- Has lower infrastructural requirement (e.g. Laboratory, transport, materials, boat)
 - EO data is often freely accessible
 - Does not require (regular) access to water bodies
- Requires trust and specific skills and knowledge
 - Handling large amounts of data requires computational capacity and strong internet connection
 - Lack of examples in some areas / applications
 - Lack of validated datasets for some areas
 - Lack of tools/platforms that simplify the process
-
- Is massively more useful when EO is used with traditional monitoring data

6.3 Networks and synergies

Networks are key to the transfer of knowledge and innovation. Networks can promote synergies or relationships which include top-down, bottom-up, and peer-to-peer capacity exchange. Water-ForCE itself has become an extensive network and also interacts with many other networks (e.g., GLEON, WWQA). Despite the number of networks that already exist, feedback within the consortium engagement activities has called for new networks and a strengthening of some existing networks. Feedback loops into the Copernicus programme, as a user-driven programme, are particularly important. Some of these networks and feedback loops are; feedback between Services (D3.3), networks bringing together Remote Scientists and end-users across sectors (WP1), feedback loop between end-users and Services (D3.3), bring together in situ community and EO community (D2.4 and D4.3).

6.1 Existing networks

The list below includes networks, projects and programmes which are regarded as contributing to capacity building. Note that almost all initiatives have implications for capacity building (for example, skills will be developed by those involved or technical outcomes of the project will expand the capacity of Copernicus). However, this list focuses on projects that are directly relevant for inland water monitoring or have a capacity building focused agenda. In summary, these projects and programmes go a long way to develop capacity among users and Copernicus. Important capacity building projects within Copernicus include the [Copernicus Academy](#) and the Framework Partnership Agreement for [Copernicus User Uptake](#). These activities are based around coordinating and exploiting synergies among different users (Section 5.4). Many other projects listed are temporary projects (e.g., 3 years) funded under the umbrella of the EU, or are spin-off start-ups which have received funding from the EU.

Table 6. List of existing projects and Programmes which meet, to some degree, the capacity building needs outlined in sections 4 & 5. Data is filled in where known.

Project name	Status	Funding & Status	Notes
Copernicus Academy Network	Ongoing	EU	
Copernicus User Uptake	Ongoing	EU	
H2020 WQeMS		H2020	
JNCC Copernicus project		EC	
Tiger initiative (Africa focus) Finished in 2016		ESA	
EO4sd (water resources management)		ESA	
E-shape		Commercial (with EU backing)	
Water insight		Commercial (with EU	

		backing)	
GEO capacity building strategy			
GEO AquaWatch (related to the above)			
EO Africa R&D Facility		ESA	Built off the Tiger initiative, focused on capacity building in Africa
GMES and Africa			
Fanfar (Africa)		Horizon2020	capacity building in Africa, water managers
Omdena -	Ongoing	USaid	Not water-specific but interesting structure using projects which individuals can join up.
EO4GEO		EU related	
COSME for skills project (Eyes on Earth)		EU related	A good capacity building framework but not water specific
H2020 project (CopHub.AC) - not water specific			
MOOC		EU related	The RUS activity entrusted to ESA (training the trainers, digital and space data manipulation skills development)
ACARE - African great lakes capacity building			Concerns including capacity building and enabling local communities within in the African Great Lakes
Capacity building workstream in WWQA - GEMS/Water			
Sat4Envi (Poland)			Capacity building in the public sector in Poland for greater EO uptake
WaterSENSE			D3.3 . The goal of WaterSENSE is to develop a modular, operational, water-monitoring system built on Copernicus Earth observation data.

EOTiST	Ongoing	H2020	Not water-specific but interesting for Ecosystem Services applications of Remote Sensing.
UNESCO-IHP (Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme)	ongoing	UNESCO	Capacity development within the IX programme “Water Secure World, in a Changing Environment”, including trainings on the use of remote sensing for water management

7. Three-step strategy for capacity building within Copernicus for Water

To conclude the findings in this report, a three step strategy is prescribed. This contains individual, organisation and system level recommendations (Figure x).

Individual-level

Firstly, there is a huge task to reach the massive potential customer-base of EO data within the water domain. Key actions to achieve this include providing a series of tutorials, improving the organisation of the Copernicus website for new users with an onboarding routine. From the many outreach activities within the Water-ForCE project, these actions are routinely mentioned and are a minimum expected from one of the largest data and information providers in the world. Examples in this respect can come from NASA ARSET programme.

Organisational-level

Secondly, there is a need to build capacity within Copernicus to improve the supply of products for the water domain. As a user-driven programme, Copernicus needs to deliver user-driven product development, as opposed to technology driven. While this is addressed more in other deliverables (e.g., D6.2, D6.4), it is also important that products are delivered at various capacity levels and through tools and platforms that lower barriers to access.

System-level

Thirdly, the priority for an enabling environment is including EO methods and compliance regulations within EU water policy. In addition, funding is required on various scales, including funding of academic research projects to funding of global in situ programmes. Networks are also key for knowledge transfer, which increases individual capacity and increases feedback for directly capacity building with the Copernicus programme.

Figure 11. Summary of the three-step strategy for capacity building within Copernicus for Water.

7. Monitoring and evaluating progress

Evaluating the effectiveness of capacity building activities at the individual, organisational and system levels can be challenging since the outcome might not be easily measured and may serve a diverse set of goals (e.g., increase awareness and also support SDG's. etc.). This inherent challenge of monitoring and evaluating capacity building activities may disincentive practices which are actually effective but are more difficult to measure. In addition, many activities which are not explicitly 'capacity building' in nature can contribute to the capacity of different groups. Some ideas for structurally monitoring and evaluating capacity building are presented here.

Monitoring and progress evaluation of capacity building activities might include determining how effective capacity building initiatives have been towards specific goals (e.g., increasing usership). Monitoring may also involve evaluating the amount of resources, events or funding that is dedicated to the capacity building agenda. Currently, there is a lack of publicly accessible information on performance indices or metrics to demonstrate the effectiveness of different activities within Copernicus. In addition to the EARSC survey, it would be helpful to conduct an annual survey to assess the capacity building needs of potential and current users and track changes over time. The change in demand will demonstrate the impact of initiatives.

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Appendix

Full CB survey can be found here:

Click the links below to find the survey in your language of choice:

English = <https://stirling.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/water-force-online-survey>

French = <https://stirling.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/water-force-online-survey-french>

Other languages are also available:

Portuguese = <https://stirling.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/water-force-online-survey-copy>

Mandarin = <https://stirling.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/water-force-online-survey-copy-2>

Spanish = <https://stirling.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/water-force-online-survey-spanish>

Figure S1. Water-ForCE capacity building recommendations relating to widening the uptake of Copernicus services and products

Figure S2. Water-ForCE capacity building recommendations relating to widening the uptake of Copernicus services and produc

Table S1. List of resources for using EO-satellite and remote sensing data for inland water quality and quantity. Many are general but can be used for inland water quality and quantity purposes.

Practical Tutorials or education programs (i.e. how to access & use data/products)	Access	
Global Lakes Sentinel Services 10-lesson plan	Yes	GLaSS, www.glass-project.eu (https://www.trevorfoundation.org/symposium/training-course-tpsf-symposium-2023)
Trevor Platt programme 'Satellite-based tools for investigating aquatic ecosystems'	Application & selectin process	https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/join-mission/training/english/arset-monitoring-coastal-and-estuarine-water-quality-using-remote
ARSET courses (multiple)	Yes	https://www.eo4geo.eu/space-academy/training-modules/download/
GMES & Africa Learning Platform (one course on water bodies with Sentinel)	Self enrollment needed	https://ioccc.org/what-we-do/training-and-education/
ICCG list of materials	Yes	https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/pathfinders/water-quality-data-pathfinder
Water Quality Data Pathfinder - NASA EarthData	Yes	http://www.eo4geo.eu/training-material-catalogue/
EO4GEO training materials on specific subjects (e.g., flood mapping)	Yes	Discover the Terrascope webinars Terrascope
Terrascope webinar series	Yes	MapEO Water - MONOCLE Project - Multiscale Observation Networks for Optical monitoring of Coastal waters, Lakes and Estuaries (monocle-h2020.eu)
MAPEO-Water: tutorials, videos, webinars	Yes	
Other relevant sources (i.e. aquatic systems, how satellites work, coding skills)	Access	
Mantel ITN youtube resources (lakes, stratification, extreme events no EO)	Yes	https://www.youtube.com/@mantelpieces2679
MIT Open Courseware	Free (no certificate, just courses)	https://ocw.mit.edu/
Datacamp	Free	https://www.datacamp.com/ https://www.linkedin.com/learning/subscription/topics?src=go-pa&trk=sem-ga_campaign_id.11707274872_asid.116696423707_crid.482343951305_kw.linkedin%20courses_d_c tid.kwd-1081020642167_n.g_mt.e_geo.1007397&mcid=6841876146393514202&cid=&gclid=Cj0KCQIAx6ug8hCcARISAGNmMbill5xyXl7Q9j7ZZXoBYN59L3xd4soHr2Xd2oF7KqPYAVV4WM-SDkaAJzbFALw_wcB&gclid=aw-ds
LinkedIn courses	Free Trial	https://www.mooc.org/
MOOC - ESA courses	Free	https://data.jncc.gov.uk/data/6ef949ed-1c22-438f-b2f7-fd4818ec4566/JNCC-Report-590-FINAL-WEB.pdf
JNCC Data Skills Framework	Free	Copernicus mooc Copernicus
Copernicus MOOC	Free	AI for Earth Monitoring MOOC CMEMS (copernicus.eu)
Copernicus AI for Earth monitoring MOOC	Free	
Formalised University Courses	Country	
University of Stirling Masters course	Scotland	
UCC Masters course	Ireland	
SENSE PhD training programme (Centre for doctoral training)		https://eo-cdt.org/
Projects with capacity building/educational focus	Funder/Type	
H2020 WQeMS	H2020	https://wqems.eu/
JNCC Copernicus project	EC	https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/copernicus-project/
Tiger initiative (Africa focus) Finished in 2016	ESA	https://www.tiger.esa.int/page_training.php
EO4sd (water resources management)	ESA	http://eo4sd-water.net/content/capacity-building
E-shape	Commercial (with EU backing)	https://e-shape.eu/index.php/capacity-building
Water insight	Commercial (with EU backing)	https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/geo_iii/13-Capacity_Building_Strategy.pdf
GEO capacity building strategy		
GEO AquaWatch (related to the above)		
EO Africa R&D Facility - capacity development for research built off Tiger Initiative	ESA	https://www.eo4africa-rd.org/about/
GMES and Africa		
Fanfar (Africa)	Horizon2020	https://fanfar.eu/
Omdena - learn through open-source projects (interesting structure)	USAid	https://omdena.com/
Copernicus User Uptake Actions (various water management actions)	EU related	https://www.copernicus-user-uptake.eu/user-uptake
Copernicus Academy Network	EU related	https://www.copernicus.eu/en/opportunities/education/copernicus-academy
EO4GEO	EU related	http://www.eo4geo.eu/training/the-eo4geo-project/
COSME for skills project (Eyes on Earth) - not water specific	EU related	
H2020 project (CopHub.AC) - not water specific		
MOOC		
The RUS activity entrusted to ESA (training the trainers, digital and space data manipulation skills development)		
ARSET	NASA	https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/join-mission/training/english/arset-monitoring-and-modelling-floods-using-earth-observations
ACARE - African great lakes capacity building		https://www.agl-acare.org/
Capacity building workstream in WWQA - GEMS/Water		
Educational or Reporting Data portals		
SDG8 reporting portal		http://sdg6-hydrology-tep.eu/
Open-access software for processing EO water quantity/quality data		
Google Earth Engine		
R packages for processing satellite data		
Giovanni NASA		
OpenEO		OpenEO Platform